

Metabolites of tropical marine algae of the family Codiaceae (Chlorophyta) : chemistry and bioactivity

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The chemistry and bioactivity of metabolites produced by some Codiacean plants (Species of the genera : *Avrainvillea*; *Chlorodesmis*; *Codium*; *Halimeda*; *Penicillus*; *Rhizocephalus* and *Tydemania* and *Udotea*) have been reviewed. The metabolites isolated include halogenated compounds, terpenoids, oxygenated sterols, sulphated polysaccharides, proteoglycans and lectins; bioactivities such as antiviral (including anti-HIV), antibacterial, antifungal, ichthyotoxic, cytotoxic, antitumor, blood anticoagulant etc. have been reported.

The marine environment, particularly in tropical areas, offers a rich diversity of species, which is in many ways comparable to those of tropical rain forests. This environment also contains a greater number of organisms for which there are no terrestrial counterparts. Ecological pressure on marine organisms, which include competition for space, maintenance of an unfouled surface, deterrence of predation, and the ability to successfully reproduce, may have led to the evolution of unique secondary metabolites which are the chemical components responsible for these actions and interactions. Tropical marine algae of the family Codiaceae are reported to be prolific in producing many interesting bioactive molecules, both lipid- and water- soluble, which may turn out to be the candidate ones in future for drug development. Given the current resurgence of interest in the field of bioactive natural products, it is felt that this article would be a timely input to the researchers.

The family Codiaceae comes under the class Chlorophyceae of the phylum Chlorophyta and this is sub-divided into three sub-families, viz. Flabellariae (genera *Avrainvillea* and *Chlorodesmis*), Udoteae (genera *Halimeda*, *Udotea*, and *Tydemania*) and Codiae (genus *Codium*)¹⁻⁴. Species of this family are commonly found in littoral and sublittoral zones, in deep sea as epilithon or epiterranean, and are widely distributed in tropical and sub-tropical coasts⁵⁻¹¹. The species of sub-family Udoteae are called calcareous algae because they contain 50-80% CaCO₃ in their thalli⁸ which has some role in physical protection from the predators¹², and these species are considered major contributors to the coral sediments and structure¹³. Several Codiacean plants are used as food¹⁴⁻¹⁹ and folk medicine¹⁴ in many countries. Plants of this family, in general, have produced a great number of metabolites including halogenated compounds, terpenoids, oxygenated sterols, glycolipids, sulphated

polysaccharides, lectins and proteoglycans, which show interesting biological activities, viz. antiviral (including anti-HIV), antibacterial, cytotoxic, ichthyotoxic, antitumor, antifungal and blood anticoagulant activity. Therefore, this algal family could be one of the most potential sources of biomedically important natural products. In the authors' laboratory, chemical investigation on both the lipid- and water-soluble metabolites of *Codium* species have been identified, some of the water-soluble metabolites with promising antithrombic activity. The present review deals with the chemistry and bioactivity of the metabolites of the species of family Codiaceae, based on the reports published till April 1998. Chemistry and bioactivities of some tropical green algal species²⁰, Chlorophyta²¹ in general, have already been reviewed. However, sulphated polysaccharides and lectins were not dealt with in those reviews.

Halogenated compounds

The presence of enzyme haloperoxidases, lipid halogen and some halogenated metabolites, e.g. brominated diphenylmethanes have been reported from the following Codiacean plants : *Avrainvillea longicaulis*, *A. nigricans*, *A. rawsonii*^{22,25-28}, *Halimeda discoidea*, *H. goreauii*, *H. gracilis*, *H. incrassata*, *H. opuntia*, *H. tuna*. *Penicillus capitatus*, *P. dumetosus*, *P. lamourouxii*, *Rhizocephalus phoenix*, *Udotea cyathiformis*, *U. flabellum*, *U. 'pacific'* and *U. wilsoni*^{22,23}. From genus *Codium*, *C. isthmocladum*, *C. taylori*, *C. repens* and *C. elongatum* are the species reported to have such compounds^{22,24}.

Avrainvilleol and its methyl ether :

A brominated diphenylmethane derivative avrainvilleol (1) and its methyl ether (2) have been isolated from *A. longicaulis*. The structure of 1 was predicted by different chemical transformations and spectral studies²⁵. Avrain-

villeol was found to be ichthyotoxic, at 800 ppm it showed significant feeding avoidance behavior in the herbivorous damselfish, *Pomacentrus coeruleus*. It exhibited moderate to strong antibacterial activity toward the pathogenic marine bacterium *Vibrio anguillarum*²⁵, and other gram-positive bacteria *Bacillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Serratia marcescens*. It showed significant cytotoxicity to

peracetylation. Compound 3 showed broad antimicrobial activity against *Bacillus subtilis*, *Candida albicans*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Serratia marcescens*, *Pseudo-monas aeruginosa* and *Escherichia coli*, between 25 to 200 µg/disc. It also showed significant cytotoxicity to KB cells (ED₅₀ 8.9 µg ml⁻¹). Compound 4 also showed antimicrobial activity against *B. subtilis* and *S. aureus*²⁶.

KB cells at 10–100 µg ml⁻¹ concentration²⁶. This compound also inhibited the activity of inosine monophosphate dehydrogenase enzyme (IMPDH)²⁸.

5'-Hydroxyisoavrainvilleol and 3-bromo-4,5-dihydroxybenzyl alcohol :

3-Bromo-4,5-dihydroxybenzyl alcohol (3) and one new diphenylmethane derivative 5'-hydroxyisoavrainvilleol (4) were isolated along with the known compound 1 from *A. nigricans*. These diphenylmethane derivatives possibly originate from the dimerization of more ubiquitous precursors such as halo-*p*-hydroxybenzyl alcohol derivatives formed in the shikimic acid pathway via tyrosine²⁰. The occurrence of the benzyl alcohol 3 along with 1 and 4 in this species supports the proposed mechanism for the formation of 1 and 4 from 3. Earlier it was thought that compound 1 may actually be a bacterial product from epibiotic microorganisms rather than an algal metabolite. The structure of compound 4 was predicted by various spectral data [Br₂ from IRms, C₁₄ from ¹³C nmr, and H₇ (non-exchangeable proton) from ¹H nmr] and chemical conversions like the formation of a pentaacetate upon

Rawsonol and isorawsonol :

Another brominated diphenylmethane derivative rawsonol 5, has been isolated from *A. rawsonii*. It is biosynthesized by dimerization of two molecules of 3 with elimination of a molecule of methanol, which helps strengthen the hypothesis that the origin of these diphenylmethanes is from shikimic pathway via tyrosine. In 5, there are three types of substitutions, viz. two 1,2,3,4,6-pentasubstituted aromatic rings, one 1,2,3,5-tetrasubstituted and one 1,3,4-trisubstituted aromatic rings. The structure and molecular formula of 5 was predicted by analyzing the spectral data of the acetylated product rawsonol hexaacetate.

Compound 5 was shown to inhibit²⁷ the activity of the enzyme 3-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl coenzyme A (HMG-CoA) reductase (IC₅₀ = 5 µM), which is responsible for the formation of mevalonate in the rate-determining step of cholesterol biosynthesis. Moreover, it inhibits the activity of IMPDH (IC₅₀ = 10 µM), which is a rate-limiting enzyme in purine biosynthesis, responsible for the formation of xanthine 5'-monophosphate (XMP) from inosine 5'-monophosphate (IMP)²⁹. The activity of IMPDH has been

linked with cellular proliferation and inhibition of this enzyme has been demonstrated to have anticancer and immunosuppressive effects²⁸.

Isorawsonol **6** was isolated from the same species *A. rawsonii* and it is biosynthesised by condensation of two molecules of **1**, as proposed for rawsonol but involving two more highly substituted rings. Its structure was established by the analysis of ¹H nmr and ¹³C nmr spectra, aided by HMQC and HMBC. There are two 1,3,4-trisubstituted aromatic rings, one 1,2,3,4,6-pentasubstituted aromatic ring and one fully substituted ring in **6** whose molecular formula was determined by negative-ion hrfabms. It showed significant IMPDH inhibitory activity at a very low concentration (IC₅₀ = 7 μM)²⁸.

Terpenoids

The presence of these compounds have been reported in plants of the Codiaceae family, particularly in *Udotea*, *Halimeda*, *Tydemania*, *Penicillus*, *Chlorodesmis* and *Rhypocephalus* spp. It has been found that the marine algae of these species are of very low preference in the diets of tropical herbivores²⁰. Chemical investigation of these conspicuous plants have led to the isolation of an impressive array of sesquiterpenoids, acyclic and cyclic diterpenoids and triterpenoids. A unifying feature of these metabolites is the common occurrence of the multiple *bis*-enol-acetate (*E,E*-1,4-diacetoxybutadiene moieties) or aldehyde or both as functional groups. The conjugated *bis*-enol-acetate functionality represents a 'masked' dialdehyde constellation to which high biological activity is generally attributed. The bioactivity of metabolites having aldehyde as functional groups are very interesting. The aldehydes, and even more so α,β -unsaturated aldehydes are known to react smoothly with biological nucleophiles, either by forming 'Schiff's bases' with basic nitrogen residues or accepting biological nucleophiles (amines, alcohols, sulfhydryl groups) at the β -carbon of the unsaturated aldehyde in a 'Michael type' addition reaction, resulting in enzyme deactivation. Little is known about the interaction of enolacetate functionalities with biological nucleophiles²⁰.

Sesquiterpenoids :

Many sesquiterpenes containing 1,4-diacetoxybutadiene moiety have been isolated from green algae³⁰⁻³⁶, e.g. flexilin (**7**) from *Caulerpa flexilis* and trifarin (**8**) from *C. trifaria*. Compound **7** has also been isolated from the morphologically unrelated algae *Udotea conglutinata*³⁵ and *U. geppii*³⁶, and shown to possess antimicrobial, cytotoxic and ichthyotoxic properties³⁵. *Rhypocephalus phoenix*, a calcareous alga, grows in herbivore-rich area and chemical investigation of

this species led to the isolation of sesquiterpenes containing diacetoxybutadiene moiety called rhypocephalin **9** and rhypocephalin **10**. These are toxic to pomacentrid fishes and induce pronounced feeding avoidance behavior in the herbivorous fish *Eupomacentrus leucostictus*³². The highly bioactive sesquiterpenoids **11** and **12** were isolated from *Penicillus capitatus*³⁵ as also from the morphologically unrelated alga *Udotea cyathiformis*. The spectral features of **11** are very identical to the known compounds cualerpenyne³¹ and rhypocephalin³². It is active against human pathogenic bacteria *B. subtilis* and *S. aureus*. Both **11** and **12** are active against marine bacteria *Serratia marinorubra*, *Vibrio splendida*, *V. harvey* and *V. leiognathi*. Compound **12** showed antifungal activity against *Leptosphaeria* sp., *Lulworthia* sp., and *Alternaria* sp., and also exhibited cytotoxicity in sea urchin egg assay and ichthyotoxic activity against damselfish³⁵.

Diterpenoids :

Both acyclic and cyclic diterpenoids are the major metabolites of Codiacean plants, and all have been shown to possess pronounced biological activities³⁴⁻⁵⁰. From *Chlorodesmis fastigiata* of Australian barrier reef, acyclic diterpenes didehydrotrifarin (**13**), chlorodesmin (**14**) and dihydrochlorodesmin (**15**) have been isolated; these are unique compounds possessing ketone functionalities and enol-acetate groups on both ends of the linear diterpenoids skeleton³⁴. From Guam collection of the same species, in addition to **13** and **14**, one new related linear diterpenoid **16** possessing both aldehyde and 1,4-diacetoxybutadiene functionalities was identified³⁶. It showed antibacterial activity against human pathogenic bacteria *B. subtilis*, *S. aureus* and *Vibrio* species, and showed cytotoxicity at a concentration of 8 μg ml⁻¹ in sea urchin egg assay³⁶. A novel metabolite (2*E*,6*E*,10*E*)-1-acetoxy-3-acetoxymethyl-7,11,15-trimethylhexadeca-2,6,10,14-tetraene (**17**) was isolated from same species along with a known metabolite **13**³⁷. Investigation on *Pseudochlorodesmis furcellata*, the taxonomically related sp., led to the isolation of two feeding

deterrent diterpenoids. The epoxy lactone (18) is the major metabolite structurally related to the epoxy lactone produced by *Udotea argentea*³⁶, and the minor one being the bishydro derivative of trifarin (19). Both have feeding deterrent property towards the herbivorous surgeonfish (*Zebrasoma flavescens*) and rabbitfish (*Siganus spinus*)³⁸. *Tydemania expeditionis* is a spongy alga that grows commonly in tropical coasts, from which the acyclic diterpenoid 20 possessing *bis*-enol-acetate with primary alcohol group was isolated³⁶.

Among the Codiacean plants, *Udotea* and *Halimeda* species are more conspicuous and from which many bioactive terpenoids, mostly acyclic forms have been isolated. Udoteal (21), an acyclic diterpenoid possessing α,β -unsaturated aldehyde and *E,E*-1,4-diacetoxybutadiene functionalities, is a major nonpolar metabolite isolated from fresh extracts of *Udotea flabellum*^{35,39}, and from the related alga *U. petiolata*⁴⁰. Compound 21 was shown to induce feeding avoidance behavior in herbivorous fish *Pomacentrus coeruleus* at 800 ppm level. Udoteal occurs to the extent of ca 6000 ppm in *U. flabellum* and shows ichthyotoxicity even at 10 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ seawater level³⁹. Udoteafuran (22) is another nonpolar metabolite isolated from *U. flabellum*; the same algal material stored in ethanol for long time afforded udoteatrial (23) and mixtures of cyclic acetals which are responsible for antimicrobial activity⁴¹. The structures of cyclic acetals 24-26 were established by studying the spectral properties of their respective acetates. Udoteatrial and its derivatives are considered the first representatives of a novel diterpene skeleton, udoteane. The formal name for udoteatrial is (2*R**, 3*S**, 6*R**, 7*R**)-(10*E*)-10,14-udoteadiene-1,19,20-

trial⁴¹. The C-7 epimer of udoteatrial^{42,46} and its analogs⁴³⁻⁴⁵ were synthesized. They were found to be cytotoxic against human carcinoma KB and A-549 cells *in vitro*^{44,45}. Compounds 27 and 28 are other monocyclic diterpenoids of this species, showing cytotoxic and ichthyotoxic activities against damselfish and inhibitory activity against *Serratia marinorubra*, *Vibrio splendida*, *V. harveyi* and *V. leiognathi*. Metabolite 28 also showed antifungal activity against *Lulworthia* species³⁵. Compound 27 (petiodial) was also isolated from *U. petiolata*⁴⁰ and synthesized^{47,48}.

One new diterpenoid epoxy lactone (29) containing *E,E*-1,4-diacetoxybutadiene functionality and α,β -epoxy- γ -lactone group has been isolated from *U. argentea*. It showed antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* and *B. subtilis* and cytotoxic activity at 8 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ concentration in sea urchin egg bioassay³⁶. A variety of diterpenoid metabolites were isolated from *Penicillus dumetosus*. Triacetate 30 containing *E,E*-1,4-diacetoxybutadiene functional group, a dihydro-udoteal 31 having acetate esters and a saturated aldehyde group, and two other isomeric aldehydes 32 and 33 which were isomeric with udoteal with respect to the positioning of the α,β -unsaturated aldehyde moiety were isolated. Metabolites 30 and 31 showed antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus* and *Bacillus* strains and also against some marine bacteria. Metabolite 31 showed cytotoxicity and was active against fungi *Dreschleria haloides* and *Lulworthia* species³⁵.

Species of genus *Halimeda* possess novel bioactive compounds reported to have various biological activities⁴⁹⁻⁵⁷. Halimedatrial 34, a bicarbocyclic trialdehyde diterpenoid, was isolated from *Halimeda tuna*, *H. opuntia*,

H. incrassata, *H. simulans*, *H. scabra*, *H. copiosa*⁵³, *H. monile*, *H. cylindracea* and *H. gigas*⁵⁵. This bicyclic compound having one cyclopentane and one cyclopropane rings is structurally related to udoteatrial, a hydrated trialdehyde which contains only one cyclopentane ring⁴¹. Halimedatrial never exists in hydrate form, but udoteatrial exists exclusively as the hydrate, or cyclic acetal-bis-hemiacetal⁵⁵. Halimedatrial produces a wide spectrum of deleterious biological effects, and is structurally similar to numerous insect antifeedants such as warburganal and iridoid aldehydes. Halimedatrial showed cytotoxic activity in sea urchin egg bioassay and antibacterial activity toward *S. marinorubra*, *V. splendida*, *V. leiognathi*, *V. harveyi*, VJP Cal 8101 and gray fungus VJP Cal 8104. It is toxic toward reef fishes *Eupomacentrus planifrons* and *Dascyllus aruanus* and significantly reduce their feeding behavior⁵³. Halimedalac-tone (35), another cyclic diterpene was isolated from *H. tuna* and *H. scabra*, appeared to have formed from the condensation of the aldehyde groups at C-2 and C-7 of halimedatrial tetraacetate 36, a diterpenoid possessing the well-known bis-enol-acetate and α,β -unsaturated aldehyde groups, was isolated as the major metabolite from many

Halimeda species. It was converted into 34 upon chemical workup, and the co-occurrence of these two metabolites in numerous individual *Halimeda* species shows that the metabolites are biosynthetically related. Bis-nor-diterpenoid 37 is an unusual metabolite isolated from *H. macroloba*, *H. discoidea* and *H. scabra* as a minor one, while 34 and 36 are the major metabolites. All these four metabolites showed potent antimicrobial, antifungal and cytotoxic activities⁵⁵. Several *Halimeda* spp. also contain epihalimedatrial 38, which is the epimer at the central aldehyde functionality. Unlike metabolite 34, this compound is readily hydrated and is highly unstable⁵⁶.

A linear diterpenealdehyde, opuntial (4,9-diacetoxy-udoteal) (39) was isolated from *Halimeda opuntia*⁵⁴. Halitunal (40), and unusual diterpene aldehyde possessing a unique cyclopenta[c]pyran ring system, was isolated from *H. tuna* and it showed significant *in vitro* activity against murine coronavirus strain A59. It is biosynthesized from tetraacetate 36 via an intermediate which, after loss of two molecules of acetic acid, rearrangement and hydrolysis, yields halitunal 40⁵⁷. From *Codium decortcatum*, an acyclic diterpene alcohol 41 was isolated which displayed strong

toxicity ($LC_{50} < 1000$ ppm) at all the concentrations against brine shrimp larvae⁵⁸. Other acyclic diterpenoids, 3,7,11,15-tetramethylhexadec-1-en-3-ol (42), 3,7,11,15-tetramethylhexadec-3-ene-1,2-diol (43), 7,11,15-trimethyl-3-methylenehexadecane-1,2-diol (44) and 3,7,11,15-tetramethylhexadecane-1,2-diol (45) were isolated from *C. decorticatum*. Compounds 42 and 43 were also isolated from *C. flabellatum* and *C. iyengarii* respectively⁵⁹.

Triterpenoids :

Triterpenoids are common in terrestrial organisms, and few of them have also been isolated from marine source. *Tydemania expeditionis* is the only Codiacean alga that has been reported to afford triterpenoids. From this species, three Δ^3 -norcycloartene triterpenoids 46-48 with different side-chain functionalities, have been isolated. Compound 46 contains α,β -unsaturated ketone, 47 has non-conjugated ketone while 48 has a hydroxyl as functional groups. All these three metabolites lack the toxicity and feeding deterrent

properties commonly associated with the terpenoids usually produced by this group of algae⁶⁰.

Cycloartanol sulfates :

Cycloartan-3,23,29-triol-3,29-disodium sulfate (49), cycloartan-3,29-diol-23-one-3,29-disodium sulfate (50) and cycloart-24-en-3,29-diol-23-one-3,29-disodium sulfate (51) were isolated from *Tydemania expeditionis*. These are potent inhibitors of pp60^{v-src}, the oncogenic protein tyrosine kinase encoded by Rous sarcoma virus. Protein tyrosine kinases comprise a large family of enzymes that regulate cell growth and intracellular signaling pathways. Inhibitors of these enzymes may have utility in cancer and other hyperproliferative conditions⁶¹.

Terpenoids for chemical defense :

Herbivory has a profound effect on seaweeds in both temperate and tropical communities^{62,63}. Codiacean plants depend mostly on either chemical deterrence or morphologi-

cal deterrence. High calcification in some of these species provides physical deterrence against predators⁶⁴⁻⁶⁹. Sesquiterpenoids and diterpenoids produced by this group of spp. as discussed above, exhibit broad bioactivity in pharmacological assays and deter herbivory in both field and laboratory assays. However, there are reports on how fishes of the family Scaridae (parrotfishes) and Ascoglossans (molluscs) feed on *Halimeda*, *Udotea*, *Penicillus*, *Chlorodesmis* and *Avrainvillea* spp. which have physical and chemical deterrents, and survive^{21,70-74}.

Fatty acids, sterols and other lipids

Fatty acids :

Most of the fatty acids synthesized by marine algae are straight-chain saturated and unsaturated fatty acids with even-numbered carbon chains. Fatty acids with an uneven number of carbon atoms, and branched chain iso- and anteiso-fatty acids are present quite frequently, but only in small proportions. The fatty acids, identified in marine algae range from C₈ to C₂₂ in their carbon number, however, the majority of them are from C₁₂ to C₁₈^{75,76}. The fatty acids identified from *Codium* species range from C₃ to C₂₉⁵⁹. Both saturated and unsaturated fatty acids including monoenoic, dienoic, trienoic and monoynoic acids are commonly found in the Codiacean plants^{59,77-80}. Saturated fatty acids are present in lower quantities than unsaturated ones⁵⁹. According to some reports, however, saturated fatty acids in these algae are always found in much greater amount

than the unsaturated ones^{77,78}. Among saturated fatty acids, palmitic acid is the major one and oleic acid is the most abundant of all the unsaturated fatty acids present^{59,75,77,78}. In some species, however, dodecenoic acid has been found to be a major component⁷⁹. Generally, the molecular weight of saturated fatty acids are lower than the unsaturated ones^{81,82}.

Sterols :

The sterol composition of the algae has been of interest for several reasons. Some algae may provide dietary sterol to various other organisms; in some instances, the sterols may be of taxonomic value. From *C. fragile*, (24*S*)-24-methylcholesta-5,25-dien-3 β -ol (codisterol, **52**) and (24*S*)-24-ethylcholesta-5,25-dien-3 β -ol (clerosterol, **53**) have been isolated as the minor and the major sterol respectively⁸³. This is the first report of the presence of condisterol in nature but the presence of clerosterol has previously been reported in higher plants. From the same species, along with **52** and **53** cholesterol was also isolated^{84a,b}. Compound **53** has always been the major sterol in *Codium* species so far investigated⁸³⁻⁸⁹. It has also been isolated from *C. vermilara*⁸⁵, *C. adhaerens*, *C. bursa*⁸⁶, *C. tomentosum*^{86,87}, *C. iyengarii*^{59,88-90}, *C. decortcatum*^{59,89}, *C. flabellatum*⁵⁹ and *C. arabicum*⁹¹, and therefore appears to be the characteristic sterol of *Codium* species. Compound **52** was detected as a minor constituent in many species of *Codium*^{84-86,92,93} and was considered to be the characteristic sterol of the genus *Codium*, and important for the

chemotaxonomic correlation of this genus because of the rareness of its occurrence in nature⁹². But it could not be detected in *C. tomentosum*⁸⁷, *C. elongatum*, *C. decorricatum* and *C. iyengarii*⁵⁹.

Cholesterol **54** is commonly present in all Codiacean plants reported so far. From *Halimeda* species, the presence of 22-dehydrocholesterol (**55**), 24-methylenecholesterol

cholesteryl acetate (**63**), decortinone (3 β -hydroxystigmasta-5,25-dien-7-one **64**) and decortinol (stigmasta-5,25-dien-3 β ,7 α -diol **65**) are the other sterols of *Codium* species^{59,89}.

Oxygenated sterols and their bioactivity : In general, oxygenated sterols possess interesting biological activities^{94a,b}. From *Codium arabicum*, along with **53**, **64** and **65** many oxygenated sterols have been isolated and

(**56**), brassicasterol (**57**) and clionasterol (**58**) have been reported⁸⁶. The presence of sterols **55** and **56** has also been reported from *Tydemania* species⁶⁰. 28-Isofucosterol (**59**), ergosterol (**60**), ostreasterol (24-methylenecholest-5-en-3 β -ol **61**), isodecortinol (stigmasta-5,25-dien-3 β ,7 β -diol **62**),

many of them showed significant cytotoxicity toward various cancer cell lines. Other oxygenated sterols isolated from this species are (24*S*)-24-ethylcholesta-4,25-dien-6 β -hydroxy-3-one (**66**), (24*S*)-24-ethyl-5 α -hydroperoxycholesta-6,25-dien-3 β -ol (**67**) and (24*S*)-24-ethyl-7 α -hydroperoxy-

cholesta-6,25-dien-3 β -ol (68). Compounds 64-68 showed potent cytotoxic activity ($ED_{50} \leq 2.1 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) against P-388 (mouse lymphocytic leukemia), KB (human nasopharyngeal carcinoma), HT-29 (human colon carcinoma) and A-549 (human lung adenocarcinoma). Compound 53 also showed significant cytotoxic activity against A-549, but not on other cells⁹¹.

Sterol glycosides : Sterol glycoside 69, the 3-*O*- β -D-galactopyranoside of (24*S*)-24-ethylcholesta-5,25-dien-3 β -ol (clerosterol), was isolated from *Codium iyengarii*⁹⁰, *C. decorticatatum*^{59,89}, *C. flabellatum*⁵⁹ and *C. dwarkense*⁹⁵.

Other lipids :

Lipids are very important in the fields of pharmacy and medicine. The occurrence of phospholipids such as phosphatidylcholine (PC) (also known as lecithin)⁹⁶ and phosphatidylserine⁹⁷ have been reported in *Codium* species. In *C. fragile*, the presence of glycolipids such as monogalactosyl diglyceride (MGDG), digalactosyl diglyceride (DGDG) and TGDG (trigalactosyl diglyceride) have been reported^{98,99}. Sulphonoglycolipids have potent biological activities including anti-HIV-1¹⁰⁰ and few of them were isolated from Indian marine algae^{101,102}.

Sulphated polysaccharides

These are polymers of aldoses and/or ketoses linked together through glycosidic linkages. Sulphated polysaccharides (SPS) is a class of compounds having hemi-ester sulphate groups in their sugar units. These are found commonly in marine algae and higher animals. *Codium* spp. contain mainly arabinose and galactose, with lesser amounts of glucose, xylose, mannose and rhamnose having ester sulphate(s) in different carbon positions. *Halimeda* and *Udotea* species were reported to have xylose¹⁰³.

Biomedical potential :

Apart from industrial uses, in recent years, polysaccharides of plant origin have emerged as an important class of bioactive natural products. Antitumor, immunological, anticomplementary, anti-inflammatory, blood anticoagulant, hypoglycemic and antiviral activities have been observed in a wide range of polysaccharides. The biomedical potential of SPS of *Codium* species are anticoagulant, anti-HIV and antitumor activities.

Anticoagulant activity : Anticoagulant activity associated with marine algal polysaccharide was first described by Chargaff *et al.*¹⁰⁴ in 1936. Research in the field of anticoagulant and antithrombotic agents became important because heparin, widely used both in the laboratory and therapeutically as an anticoagulant, has some disadvantages

like chemical inhomogeneity and haemorrhagic side-effects. In *Codium* species anticoagulant activity was reported¹⁰⁵ and a group of Codiacean plant of Indian waters were screened for this activity¹⁰⁶. Proteoglycans and SPS of *Codium* species were reported to have encouraging activity¹⁰⁶⁻¹¹⁰. Proteoglycans exhibit high APTT (activated partial thromboplastin time), PT (prothrombin time), and TT (thrombin time); their anticoagulant effect occurs in the common pathway and may be primarily antithrombin in nature¹⁰⁹. Arabinan sulphate isolated from *C. latum* of Japanese waters showed 9.5 to 15.0 times more activities than heparin^{107,110}. Sulphated polysaccharides isolated from *C. dwarkense* and *C. tomentosum* collected from the Indian coasts also showed potent blood anticoagulant activity and the active components in those SPS were characterised as sulphated arabinan and sulphated arabinogalactan¹⁰⁶.

Anti-HIV activity : The polysaccharide of *C. fragile* is effective against retroviruses and shows 70-100% inhibitory activity against HIV. It has an inhibiting activity against adsorption of HIV on human-derived lymphocytes and functions to inhibit the activity of reverse transcriptase (RT)¹¹¹, a strong inhibition against RT was seen¹¹¹ at concentrations of 50-1000 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. Since virus-cell binding is based on the interaction between the glycoprotein gp 120 of the virus envelop and CD4 receptor of the target cells, these polymers may also interact with gp 120 and CD4 receptor to block giant cell formation between HIV-1 infected cells and uninfected CD4-positive cells^{112,113}. Structure-activity relationship was found for all enveloped viruses tested with regard to the molecular weight and degree of sulphation of the polysaccharide. The antiviral activity increased with increasing molecular weight or degree of sulphation; ideally, two (or more) sulphate groups per monosaccharide unit¹¹⁴ are required to accomplish full anti-HIV activity. The strongly negative R-O-SO₃ groups bind to the basic V3 loop of the gp 120 molecule, which inhibits HIV attachment to the CD4 receptor^{112,113}.

Antitumor activity : An acid polysaccharide fraction of the water extract of *C. pugniformis* showed activity against ascites tumor of Ehrlich carcinoma and solid tumors produced by Ehrlich carcinoma and Sarcoma-180. This acid hydrolysate contained galactose, arabinose and mannose¹¹⁵.

Lectins

The available information on agglutinins in marine algae is limited compared to other sources, such as higher plants, invertebrates and vertebrates. The presence of hemagglutinins in marine algae was first demonstrated by Boyd *et al.*¹¹⁶ who surveyed marine algae for hemagglutinins

against human erythrocytes. The general properties of algal lectins include lack of inhibition by simple sugars, and major sensitivity to animal erythrocytes especially the enzyme treated ones and less sensitivity to human erythrocytes¹¹⁷. Some algal lectins appear to have interesting characteristics or anomalous properties not shown by other lectins. Some of the marine algal lectins are much smaller than those derived from terrestrial plant. This characteristic alone may make them more suitable for uses such as drug targeting than those derived from terrestrial plants, because the smaller molecules are expected to be less antigenic in nature.

Biochemical investigation :

The agglutinins from two sub-species of *C. fragile*, viz. *C. fragile* subsp. *atlanticum* and *C. fragile* subsp. *tomentosoides* were isolated and biochemically characterized. Hemagglutination-inhibition studies revealed that both the lectins are inhibited by *N*-acetyl-D-galactosamine (GalNAc), but the lectin of *C. fragile* subsp. *atlanticum* is also inhibited by GluNAc¹¹⁸⁻¹²¹. A new lectin named 'tomentine' from *C. tomentosum* has been studied in detail¹²². It was inhibited by GlcNAc and also to a lesser degree by melibiose, raffinose, *N*-acetylmannosamine and trehalose¹²². The lectin from *C. taylora* is inhibited by fetuin and lactoferrin¹²³.

Biomedical importance :

Each lectin has its own specific binding receptor, and because of this property they have different biological activities. The prospective uses of lectins isolated from the *Codium* species *C. fragile* (ssp. *atlanticum* and *tomentosoides*) and *C. tomentosum* in biomedical fields are summarized below. *C. tomentosum* lectin was reported to be used in glycoprotein polymorphism¹²⁴ and fishery research¹²⁵. *C. fragile* lectins was found to be useful in human^{120,121,126} and animal¹²⁷ blood groupings, in drug delivery system¹²⁸ and as a larvicide^{129,130}. Both *C. fragile* and *C. tomentosum* lectins have been reported to be useful in clinical microbiology¹³¹ and some other *Codium* lectins were reported to be used in clinical parasitology¹³².

Summary

The lectins of *Codium* species are used as diagnostic reagents and their usefulness in drug delivery system is under trial. However, the utility of other bioactive metabolites like halogenated compounds, terpenoid, oxygenated sterols, SPS and proteoglycans in deriving new drug models should also be explored. More comprehensive pharmacological studies are to be performed to determine the potential mammalian activities and therapeutic applications of these unique metabolites.

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